

The idea in a nutshell

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com:text addresses the central problem that academic writing in its current form often remains isolated and monologic, focused on grades and academic recognition rather than on a dialog with the readership. At a time when digital communication is becoming ever more immediate, the didactics of writing in bachelor's and master's degree programs fail to prepare students for their role in society because they don't see writing as a tool for social engagement and public discourse. com:text addresses this by using reader-centered workshops, expert tutors from the field, an open-source platform and public write-a-thons to promote the development of post-academic writing skills that resonate not only within academia but also in writing-intensive professions and with the wider public.